

GRAMMAR CATEGORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article discusses the classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek, primary grammatical categories, the division of existing words in each specific language into specific groups, lexical and lexical-grammatical, morphological forms according to their meanings to the generality of words belonging to a particular group.*

Ushbu maqolada hozirgi o'zbek va o'zbek tillaridagi so'z guruhlari klassifikatsiyasi, birlamchi grammatik kategoriyalar, har bir aniq tildagi mavjud so'zlarning muayyan guruhga bo'linishi, muayyan guruhga mansub so'zlarning umumiylikiga ma'nolariga ko'ra leksik va leksik-grammatik, morfologik shakllar haqida so'z yuritilgan.

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Primary grammatical categories are word groups or lexical-grammatical groups of words. The words available in each specific language are divided into specific groups, which are called word groups. The classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek is determined by the following characteristics of words, a) lexical and lexico-grammatical meanings, b) the generality of morphological forms for words belonging to a particular group, c) the role of words in speech. Word groups are also called lexical-grammatical categories of words because their lexical and grammatical forms are taken into account when

dividing words into groups [Chomsky 1957: 416]. For example, all words in the horse category refer to the subject name. It should be noted, however, that not all horses need to be subject. Although some words do not denote an object, they are still used in place of an object. For example, love in English, place of joy, friendship in Uzbek, happiness and so on. Words belonging to the category of adjectives mainly represent the sign and feature of the object. For example: blue blue, white white, clever smart, in Uzbek: long, wide, active, etc. Words belonging to the category of verbs denote an action, state or process: run run, sleep sleep in Uzbek: to come, to blush, to see, and so on.

Each category has its own morphological forms of words, which form morphological paradigms and are associated with known grammatical categories.

For example, the suffix -s added to a horse in English means a category of numbers, and the suffix -ed in a verb means a category of time.

The Uzbek language also has its own form of morphological paradigm, verbs and other word groups. For example: book - books; work - worked.

In addition, the words in each word group also perform a specific syntactic function in the sentence. For example: a noun can be mainly as a possessive, a complement, a predicative part of a participle, an adjective, a predicative part of a participle, a verb can be a participle of a sentence. Two or more word combinations can perform the same function in a sentence. For example, a horse can come as a determinant, as a number.

The communication process takes place with the direct participation of all language tiers. Even when a single tier is linguistically analyzed, the tiers are interconnected. For example, morphological tier units have their full description only in syntax. In modern English, a single word can refer to several word groups at the same time.

This is especially evident in the modern English noun and verb, as the reduction results in the disappearance of the distinctive characters at the end of the English noun and verb. It is very difficult to determine whether a word belongs to a

lexical-grammatical word group. Words in modern English are not rich in morphological features. Therefore, the form of a word group may not differ from the second word group when it comes to its initial form or the first form of its paradigm. For example, if we take the words water, telephone, measure, mistake, they are both nouns and verbs at the same time, that is, water - water, to put water, to irrigate; telephone, to make a telephone call; measure - «measure, measure; mistake error; can come in the sense of making a mistake. Such cases are relative between horse and quality 1) relative; 2) related, relative; wet between adjective and verb 1) wet; 2) soaking, moistening; one between a horse and a stalk 1) a; something is an object, the person also encounters it regularly [Shaumyan 1965: 56].

Some are made in the presence of conversion, some are made as a result of the loss of flexion, and the amount of such common words that are compatible in terms of form is very large.

These include the following words: button - button, to button button, button, button, butter, to butter, butt swim, head hit, to butt swim, head hit, love love, to love, and so on.

In both English and Uzbek, the same form comes in the form of a noun or a verb. They can only be distinguished syntactically. Comparative grammar also contributes to the creation of bilingual dictionaries. The lexicographer must simultaneously describe the lexical and grammatical characteristics of the words included in the dictionary in both languages. Some of the word groups may have all three of the features mentioned above, and some may not be used as an independent part of speech in a sentence, although they do have lexical meaning and morphological form. In this regard, word groups are divided into two parts: 1) independent parts of speech (Notional parts of speech), 2) auxiliary parts of speech (Structural parts of speech or function words).

Words belonging to independent word groups express lexically independent meanings, naming objects without the help of other words, indicating their

quantity, sign, degree of fulfillment, the speaker's relation to the content of his speech. Independent word groups have paradigmatic forms that are grammatically related to certain grammatical categories and can perform a specific function in a sentence. The next tense form represents that an action or process will occur after the time the speech is spoken. In English, the future tense is formed by adding leading verbs in the infinitive form to the auxiliary verbs shall and will. In this case, the first person shall be used in singular and plural shall. Shall, a verb combination formed using will, is called an analytic form because shall, will added to the leading verb loses its lexical meaning and is used only as an indicator of grammatical tense. That is why the analytic form shall (will) be a simple cut in the sentence: "Well", said the stgapper, "I'll come but no handcuffs" (H. I. Wells). The aspect category is related to the time category, more precisely to the time category. Verbs vary in both the tense category and the aspect category.

Aspect refers to the nature of the occurrence of an action in verbs, i.e., the beginning, continuation, completion, and repetition of an action. Verbs in English are studied in two different aspects: a) Common Aspect and b) Continuous Aspect. The general aspect provides general information about whether or not an action has occurred. In the continuous aspect, however, it indicates that the action is continuing at a certain time.

The general aspect is definite and the continuous aspect is definite. The continuous aspect is formed by adding the adjective I form of the independent verb to any form of the auxiliary verb to be. For example:

to read — to be reading

He reads - He is reading

(She reads - She reads)

He read —He was reading

(He read - He was reading)

He will read - He will be reacting.

(He reads— He reads)

The present tense in general.(The Present Tense of the Common Aspect). The present tense form in the general aspect of the verb is made up of the omitted infinitive. Only the third person singular form - (e) s suffix is added. For example:

I come, she comes

We come, she comes

This they rather enjoy: indeed, they finish it quite successfully.

In conclusion, the artistic and publicistic styles are not functionally perfect, they can be used elements that are characteristic of all styles. The publicistic style is associated with the socio-political sphere of communication, the mass media has its own characteristics as a form of expression.

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